

APPENDICES

Appendix A. Detailed Search Strings for ProQuest and Web of Science

ProQuest Search String

(noft(project manage* OR product owner OR scrum master OR project planning OR project control OR program management OR portfolio selection OR portfolio management) AND noft(generative AI OR large language model* OR ChatGPT OR GPT OR AI-powered OR cognitive agents OR Conversational AI) AND noft(cognitive bias* OR heuristic* OR judgment OR decision making OR behavioral bias* OR human AI interaction))

Advanced Search in “Search by command”

A peer-reviewed filter was applied

01-01-2023 to 11-03-2025

Language: English

Document type: Article

Web of Science String

TS=(("project manage*" OR "product owner" OR "scrum master" OR "project planning" OR "project control" OR "program management" OR "portfolio selection" OR "portfolio management") AND ("generative AI" OR "large language model*" OR "ChatGPT" OR "GPT" OR "AI-powered" OR "cognitive agents" OR "conversational AI") AND ("cognitive bias*" OR heuristic* OR judgment OR "decision making" OR "behavioral bias*"OR "human AI interaction"))

Advanced Search Query Builder

01-01-2023 to 03-11-2025

Document type: No filter applied

Language: English

Under Database, the option Research Commons was disabled

Appendix B. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined using mirrored logic to ensure conceptual precision while retaining comprehensive coverage of relevant studies, following established guidance for evidence-based synthesis (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006; Okoli, 2015). Studies were included if they: (1) were published from 2023 onward; (2) were peer-reviewed journal articles or published conference papers; (3) examined conversational Generative AI; (4) addressed project-related decision-making in project management contexts; and (5) explicitly discussed cognitive biases or provided textual evidence from which cognitive biases could be inferred. Studies were excluded if they failed to meet any of these criteria, were not written in English, or were not retrievable in full text.

Appendix C. Taxonomy of Cognitive Biases Across Tiers 1 and 2

TIER	BIAS	DEFINITION	KEY AUTHORS
Tier 1	Optimism Bias	Systematic tendency to overestimate favorable outcomes while underestimating potential difficulties, risks, or costs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kahneman & Tversky (1979) • Flyvbjerg (2006, 2017, 2021)
Tier 1	Planning Fallacy	Tendency to underestimate the time, effort, and resources required to complete tasks or projects, even when experience suggests otherwise.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kahneman & Tversky (1979) • Flyvbjerg (2006, 2017, 2021)
Tier 1	Anchoring	Overreliance on an initial value or piece of information, which subsequently shapes and constrains judgement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kahneman & Tversky (1979) • Flyvbjerg (2006, 2021)
Tier 1	Availability Bias	Judgement influenced by information that is most salient or easily recalled rather than by objective or representative evidence.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tversky & Kahneman (1974)
Tier 1	Overconfidence	Inflated belief in one's own knowledge, accuracy, or predictive abilities, leading to miscalibrated decision-making.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kahneman (2011) • Moore & Healy (2008)
Tier 1	Hindsight Bias	Inclination to view past events as more predictable or inevitable after their outcomes are known.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fischhoff (1975)
Tier 1	Uniqueness Bias	Assumption that one's project or situation is fundamentally different from comparable cases, thereby limiting learning from prior evidence.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyvbjerg (2017, 2021)
Tier 1	Base-Rate Fallacy	Neglect or underweighting of statistical base-rate information in favor of case-specific or anecdotal details.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kahneman & Tversky (1973)
Tier 1	Escalation of Commitment	Continued investment in a failing course of action due to prior resource commitments, despite evidence of diminishing returns.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Staw (1976) • Brockner (1992)
Tier 2	Automation Bias	Tendency to over-rely on AI-generated outputs, accepting automated recommendations even when they are incomplete, low-quality, or incorrect.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parasuraman & Riley (1997).
Tier 2	Algorithm Aversion	Tendency to reject or avoid algorithmic advice after observing errors, showing lower tolerance for machine mistakes than for human ones.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dietvorst, Simmons & Massey (2015).
Tier 2	Trust Bias	Disposition to grant unwarranted trust or distrust to an AI system based on perceived reliability, confidence cues, or presentation style rather than evidence of actual performance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lee & See (2004); • Hoff & Bashir (2015).
Tier 2	Anthropomorphism Bias	Attribution of human-like intentions, understanding, or expertise to an AI system, leading users to overestimate its cognitive or interpretive capabilities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epley, Waytz & Cacioppo (2007).
Tier 2	Expertise Bias *	Tendency to misjudge the competence of an AI system, attributing expertise or authority beyond its actual capabilities and deferring to its recommendations inappropriately.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endsley (1995, 1998); • Bansal et al. (2021) • Klein & Reddy (2024).
Tier 2	Illusion of Understanding *	Overestimation of the AI's understanding due to the fluency, coherence, or confidence of the model's responses.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rozenblit & Keil (2002) • Binz & Schulz, (2023) • Powell & Riccardi (2025).

Tier 2	Framing Effects *	Sensitivity of decisions to how options or information are presented, with AI-generated wording, emphasis, or narrative structure influencing user preferences and evaluations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Tversky & Kahneman (1981);• Lu et al. (2024).
Tier 2	Loss Aversion *	Tendency to weigh potential losses more heavily than equivalent gains, particularly the perceived loss of status, autonomy, or professional relevance when interacting with or relying on conversational generative AI.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Kahneman & Tversky (1979);• Leoni et al. (2024).

Appendix D. Mapping of Explicit Bias Terms to the Cognitive Bias Taxonomy

This appendix lists all explicit cognitive biases identified in the included studies and illustrates how each term aligns with the review’s two-tier cognitive bias taxonomy.

ART. ID	VERBATIM (WITH LOCATION)	EXPLICIT BIAS	NORMALIZED TAXONOMY TERM
3	“Participants may have enjoyed their first interaction with the LLM-based chatbot due to its novelty...” (Dortheimer et al., 2024, p. 11)	Novelty effect	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
4	Automation Bias occurs when users blindly trust AI results...” (Frater & Mushininga, 2025, p. 59)	Automation bias	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
5	“Confirmation bias...” (Handler et al., 2024, p. 5)	Confirmation bias	•Confirmation bias (Tier 1)
8	“Organizations must address the risks of overreliance on AI...” (Hettrich et al., 2025, p. 2)	Overreliance	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
8	“Overreliance on GenAI could limit employees’ learning...” (Hettrich et al., 2025, p. 11)	Overreliance	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
8	“There is a risk of over-reliance on potentially incorrect results...” (Hettrich et al., 2025, p. 10)	Overreliance	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
13	“This human reflection process is susceptible to recency bias...” (Martin et al., 2025, p. 12)	Recency bias	•Availability Bias (Tier 1)
13	“Loss aversion...” (Martin et al., 2025, p. 2)	Loss aversion	•Loss aversion (Ties 1)
13	“This corresponds to the optimism bias concept...” (Martin et al., 2025, p. 14)	Optimism bias	•Optimism Bias (Tier 1)
13	“Group 2’s decreased residual risk ratings... may suggest optimism bias...” (Martin et al., 2025, p. 14)	Optimism bias	•Optimism Bias (Tier 1)
14	“Users may habitually accept AI-generated answers without rationalizing or critiquing them.” (Mbizo et al., 2024, p. 365)	Overreliance	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
14	“Over-reliance on generative AI assistance by developers.” (Mbizo et al., 2024, p. 361)	Overreliance	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
16	Mechanisms to avoid automation bias are largely needed...” (NguyenDuc et al., 2023, p. 59)	Automation bias	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
17	“Becoming overconfident in GenAI tools may result in a lack of criticism...” (Nyqvist et al., 2024, p. 43)	Overconfidence	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
20	“Users tend to overestimate the accuracy of LLM responses...” (Steyvers et al., 2025, p. 221)	Overconfidence	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
20	“Users consistently overestimated how accurate LLM outputs were...” (Steyvers et al., 2025, p. 221)	Overestimate	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
20	“Human miscalibration is primarily due to overconfidence...” (Steyvers et al., 2025, p. 224)	Overconfidence	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
20	“Overconfidence in LLM capabilities is an important concern...” (Steyvers et al., 2025, p. 226)	Overconfidence	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
20	“Overconfidence in LLM capabilities is an important concern...” (Steyvers et al., 2025, p. 226)	Overestimate	•Availability Bias (Tier 1)
21	“Potential for over-reliance on automated systems...” (Vergara et al., 2025, p. 2)	Overreliance	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)
21	“Over-reliance on automated decision making can reduce human oversight...” (Vergara et al., 2025, p. 14)	Overreliance	•Automation Bias (Tier 2)

Appendix E. Inferred Cognitive Biases: Textual Triggers, and Coding Justifications

This appendix provides illustrative examples of the textual or contextual triggers used to infer cognitive biases in studies where the authors did not explicitly name a bias. Each entry demonstrates how inferences were grounded in observable indicators and justified using the review’s interpretive framework.

ART. ID	VERBATIM EXCERPT WITH TRIGGER HIGHLIGHTED + LOCATION	INFERRED BIAS	JUSTIFICATION
2	“ <u>As a steering committee member</u> , GenAI understands its role and provides presentations upon request...” (Bahi et al., 2024, p. 59)	Anthropomorphism	Attributing understanding, role awareness, and advice-giving capacity to AI
2	“It seems that <u>GenAI understands</u> the prompt pattern... able to create an action plan...” (Bahi et al., 2024, p. 59)	Illusion of Understanding	Fluent output misread as deep reasoning
3	“However, <u>a part of the prompt influences</u> how the human engages with the chatbot...” (Dortheimer et al., 2024, p. 4)	Framing Effect	Prompt wording shapes interpretation
4	“Concerns about <u>AI replacing human roles</u> were also prominent, with 53% believing that AI will significantly replace IT jobs...” (Frater & Mushininga, 2025, p. 66)	Loss Aversion	The mention of AI “replacing human roles” signals a perceived threat of job loss, prompting loss-oriented reactions.
5	Within the context of decision support, this means that language models... <u>may parrot plausible-sounding guidance</u> ... without actually offering well-informed or well-reasoned advice. This poses a danger to practitioners, who may act uncritically on generated suggestions.” (Handler et al., 2024, p. 4)	Automation Bias	The AI’s fluent and coherent output creates an illusion of correctness that prompts users to accept suggestions uncritically.